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Ekaterina Bataeva

INSTRUMENTAL EDUCATIONAL STRATEGIES AND PRACTICES IN PRIVATE AND STATE HIGHER EDUCATION

The article considers the concept of educational strategies in the context of the theory of instrumentalization of practices of modern students. The concept of “educational strategy” means a choice by a social actor of a certain style of behavior in the educational environment, corresponding to his/her value orientations and life goals, characterized by a certain long-term sustainability. We analyze three types of educational strategies – strategy of “investing in a diploma”, “career success strategy”, and the strategy of self-realization in the professional sphere. The strategy of “investing in a diploma” is the most popular strategy in modern Ukrainian education, which is associated with the life strategy of material well-being. A less common form of educational strategies is the “career success strategy”, a distinctive feature of which is the attitude to learning and higher education not just as an opportunity to get a diploma, but as an important step in making a professional career. In the strategy of self-realization in the professional sphere, the value of self-development within the chosen specialty is emphasized. The factors of instrumentalization of education, such as minimalism in educational requests of students, externalization of their attitudes and modernization of value orientations, are identified. Since externals predominate among modern Ukrainian youth, the most typical for modern students are the instrumental attitude to education. R. Inglehart’s deficit hypothesis was used to explain the instrumentalization of higher education: the fact that students are massively oriented towards instrumental practices of achieving material well-being is a reflection of the social situation of the “deficit of material wealth”.

Key words: educational strategies, higher education, instrumental action, communicative action, student.

***Батаєва К. В.* Інструментальні освітні стратегії і практики в приватній та державній системі вищої освіти**

У статті розглянуто концепцію освітніх стратегій в контексті теорії

інструменталізації практик сучасних студентів. Поняття «освітня стратегія» означає вибір соціальним суб'єктом певного стилю поведінки в сфері освіти, що відповідає його ціннісним орієнтаціям. Проаналізовано три типи освітніх стратегій – стратегія «інвестування в корочку», «стратегія кар'єрного зростання» і «стратегія самореалізації в професійній сфері». Стратегія «інвестування в корочку» є найпопулярнішою в українській системі вищої освіти, яка корелює з життєвою стратегією матеріального благополуччя. Менш поширеною формою освітніх стратегій є «стратегія кар'єрного росту», відмінною рисою якої є ставлення до вищої освіти як до шабля в професійній кар'єрі. У третій освітній стратегії (стратегії самореалізації в професійній сфері) підкреслюється цінність саморозвитку в рамках обраної спеціальності. Виявлені фактори інструменталізації освіти, такі як мінімалізм в освітніх запитах студентів, екстерналізація їх життєвих установок і модернізація ціннісних орієнтацій. Оскільки серед сучасної української молоді переважають екстернали, тому найбільш типовим для сучасних студентів є інструментальне ставлення до освіти. Використано гіпотезу дефіциту Р. Інглхарта для пояснення інструменталізації вищої освіти: у пострадянських країнах, у яких рівень добробуту населення ще недостатньо високий, цілком очікувано стає пріоритетність матеріально-орієнтованих життєвих стратегій. Той факт, що студенти масово орієнтовані на інструментальні практики досягнення матеріального благополуччя є відображенням суспільної ситуації «дефіциту матеріальних благ».

Ключові слова: освітні стратегії, вища освіта, інструментальна дія, комунікативна дія, студент.

***Батаєва Е. В.* Інструментальні освітні стратегії та практики в приватній та державній системі вищої освіти**

В статті розглянуто концепцію освітніх стратегій в контексті теорії інструменталізації практик сучасних студентів. Поняття «освітня стратегія» означає вибір соціальним суб'єктом певного стилю поведінки в сфері освіти, що відповідає його ціннісним орієнтаціям. Проаналізовано три типи освітніх стратегій – стратегія «інвестування в корочку», «стратегія кар'єрного зростання» і «стратегія самореалізації в професійній сфері». Стратегія «інвестування в корочку» є найпопулярнішою в українській системі вищої освіти, яка корелює з життєвою стратегією матеріального благополуччя. Менш поширеною формою освітніх стратегій є «стратегія кар'єрного росту», відмінною рисою якої є ставлення до вищої освіти як до шабля в професійній кар'єрі. У третій освітній стратегії (стратегії самореалізації в професійній сфері) підкреслюється цінність саморозвитку в рамках обраної спеціальності. Виявлені фактори інструменталізації освіти, такі як мінімалізм в освітніх запитах студентів, екстерналізація їх життєвих установок і модернізація ціннісних орієнтацій. Оскільки серед сучасної української молоді переважають екстернали, тому найбільш типовим для сучасних студентів є інструментальне ставлення до освіти. Використано гіпотезу дефіциту Р. Інглхарта для пояснення інструменталізації вищої освіти: у пострадянських країнах, у яких рівень добробуту населення ще недостатньо високий, цілком очікувано стає пріоритетність матеріально-орієнтованих життєвих стратегій. Той факт, що студенти масово орієнтовані на інструментальні практики досягнення матеріального благополуччя є відображенням суспільної ситуації «дефіциту матеріальних благ».

карьеру. В стратегії самореалізації в професійній сфері підкреслюється цінність саморозвитку в рамках вибраної спеціальності. Виявлені фактори інструменталізації сфери освіти, такі як мінімалізм в освітніх запитаннях студентів, екстерналізація їх життєвих установок і модернізація ціннісних орієнтацій. Оскільки серед сучасної української молоді переважають екстернали, тому найбільш типовим для сучасних студентів є інструментальне ставлення до освіти. Використано гіпотезу дефіциту Р. Інґхарта для пояснення інструменталізації вищої освіти: в пострадянських країнах, в яких рівень благополуччя населення ще недостатньо високий, повністю очікуваною стає пріоритетність матеріально-орієнтованих життєвих стратегій. Той факт, що студенти масово орієнтовані на інструментальні практики досягнення матеріального благополуччя є відображенням суспільної ситуації «дефіциту матеріальних благ».

Ключевые слова: освітні стратегії, вища освіта, інструментальне діяння, комунікативне діяння, студент.

In modern sociology and philosophy, there is a resurgence of interest to the theory of instrumental and communicative action of J. Habermas and M. Horkheimer, in which the situation of instrumentalization of a person's social life was considered and the perspectives of its communicativization were discussed. It can be stated that in the modern higher education, the most typical are instrumental strategies and practices of students that treat education as a "tool" for obtaining future material and career bonuses, while the terminal value of education as a communicative process is set under question. In order to understand *how* to resist instrumentalization of students' educational practices, *what* needs to be done for communicativization of educational process in universities, it is necessary to first identify the main semantic characteristics of the concepts of "educational strategies" and consider their main (and the most typical) forms [6; 7; 8; 9].

The concept of "educational strategy" means a choice by a social actor of a certain style of behavior in the educational environment, corresponding to his/her value orientations and life goals, characterized by a certain long-term sustainability. Educational strategies are formed in the process of socialization of a social actor and are the result of internalization of the most typical positions of his/her social environment at the level of society,

social groups in which he/she functions, as well as at the level of interpersonal interaction with parents, peers, and teachers [1; 2; 3]. It can be said that educational strategies are at the same time a result of both a conscious decision of a person (decision which university and specialty to choose, how hard and systematically (or, conversely, not-intensively) to learn, what educational level should be oriented – bachelor or master) and a unconscious accepting of the most typical attitudes towards higher education in general and to specific universities in particular. If a social actor has already chosen a certain educational strategy, he/she will act at the everyday level accordingly implementing certain educational practices (for example, he/she will regularly and intensively study or, on the contrary, skip classes). Thus, if the concept of “educational strategy” focuses on a perspective vision and analysis of the most typical learning forms of students in a particular society, then the concept of “educational practices” deals with everyday actions of social actors that implement appropriate educational strategies.

K. Fursov identifies eight forms of educational strategies, namely self-actualization strategy in the professional sphere, strategy of avoiding activity, development strategy, expert strategy, self-determination strategy, graduate education strategy, diploma investment strategy and strategy of a professional career. Their choice is determined by “the influence of such factors as university specialization, resources of a family, personal actions during studies” [13, p. 224]. E. Korbut considered three educational strategies – “getting a diploma”, “getting education” and “getting knowledge”. In our study, we analyze three types of educational strategies that relate to three life strategies described by T. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, Y. Reznik and T. Reznik [10] – these are strategies of life well-being, social success and self-realization.

Let us start with the strategy of “investing in a diploma”, the most popular strategy in modern Ukrainian education, which is associated with the life strategy of material well-being. A student who has chosen this strategy is primarily focused not so much on gaining profound professional knowledge, not so much on self-improvement in a profession, but on acquiring an optimal (better to say, minimal) set of skills that can be invested in the future in his/her “workplace”. The student-investor sees the main

goal of his/her staying at the university in the accumulation of the required number of points needed to get an exam/credit for the studied disciplines, which, in turn, will be necessary in the future to just get a diploma. The content of the educational process itself is less important, he/she has no interest in learning. It will not be a mistake to define educational practices of a student investor as instrumental, since they manifest the attitude to education as a tool for getting a certain set of life benefits in the future, while education itself is regarded as a “subsidiary tool” for obtaining a profitable workplace. A diploma is perceived only as a mean for getting a prestigious social position in the future.

The instrumentalization of educational practices of student investors generates a specific attitude towards different subjects of the educational process – teachers, other students – who are perceived in the context of the value system of “bargains”. Relationships are established and maintained only with those of them who can ensure getting better (and more prestigious) signs of status superiority, whose symbolic, social or economic capital is the highest. As for educational practices of students-investors, they are characterized, on the one hand, by permanent boredom and fatigue, manifested in apathy and lack of interest in topics studied, and on the other hand, periodic energization of learning activities in those situations in which a student can get more points for a certain type of academic work.

If we talk about the student-investor’s psycho-type, then it is quite obvious that he/she is characterized by external attitudes, low achievement motivation and social infantilism, manifested in the unwillingness to take responsibility for the results of his/her own life activity. Social infantilism is characterized by a poorly developed subjectivity (inability to control and design one’s own life, “one day” existence, poor understanding of the fact that the author of one’s own destiny is not someone else, but him/herself), a consumer attitude towards life. A student who has chosen this strategy follows the life attitude of rational interest, relying not on his/her own strength and perseverance, not on cognitive activity, but on support provided by others (parents, sponsors or other subjects of the educational process).

According to the results of sociological research, the educational strategy of “investing in a diploma” is dominant in modern society. This is quite consistent with the thesis of J. Habermas on the instrumentalization

of life in the modern world [14]. For example, in the study “Value orientations and life plans of modern students”, conducted in 2012–2013 by scientists of the N. Karazin Kharkiv National University (3058 Ukrainian students, 628 Russian students, and 300 Belarus students were interviewed), it was found that “the most common type of modern student is a student who is not oriented toward mastering knowledge, but getting a diploma (about 60% of respondents), and who is not motivated to become a highly qualified professional in a chosen field. Such a student is distinguished by unpreparedness to intensive learning activities, the desire to save intellectual strength, academic dishonesty, the desire to transform the educational process into an entertainment program, the perception of an undeserved, including “purchased” grade as a norm, a low level of academic achievement” [11, p. 58]. Students-investors (or “pragmatists” as defined by L. Sokuryanskaya) are advocates of a utilitarian and mercantile attitude to life, a feature of which is the “poetization” of benefit and calculation in all contexts of social existence.

A less common form of educational strategies is the “career success strategy” (correlated with the life strategy of social success), a distinctive feature of which is the attitude to learning and higher education not just as an opportunity to get a diploma, but as an important step in making a professional career. Students-careerists are quite diligent ones, attentive to all educational tasks, showing rather high rates of educational activity. At the same time, they are not characterized by treating the profession as a vocation, as an opportunity for creative formation of their own personality, but only as a tool to achieve prestigious social positions. In contrast to student-investors, students-careerists are interested in getting the profession that they are studying at the university and which they are not going to change after receiving a diploma. Similarly to students-investors, students-careerists are characterized by an instrumental attitude to the education as a tool to get “assets” that do not coincide with the learning process itself.

For educational practices of “careerists”, it is not typical to engage in “here and now” interaction with teachers and other students, which is perceived rather as technology of accumulating symbolic signs of professionalism. Like “investors”, they are more interested in “external

stimulation” through assessments and accumulated points, rather than intrinsic motivation for self-development. We can conclude that in post-Soviet countries the percentage of “careerists” is about 20% (according to the results of the aforementioned study of L. Sokuryanskaya, “the most significant reasons for getting higher education for representatives of this cluster is to become a highly qualified specialist in a chosen field, to secure material well-being in the future, as well as the desire to improve social status and have a more prestigious position in society” [11, p. 58].

In the third educational strategy (the strategy of self-realization in the professional sphere), in contrast to the previous strategies, deconstruction of instrumentalist practices is carried out, which is combined with the communicativization of educational activities. For students who have chosen a strategy of self-realization, the main criterion for the quality of education is the opportunity to enjoy learning and the knowledge, the possibility of self-development and self-improvement within the chosen specialty. At the same time, these students seek to deepen their knowledge not only in their specialties, but also in related scientific fields, aiming at intellectual “self-expansion”, the acquisition of scientific erudition and versatility of knowledge. Students-creators are less interested in external “reinforcements” of educational activity (in reward through points or scholarships). They are much more stimulated by the subjective desire to “be” educated, “become” a high-class specialist, “get joy” from professional activities that indicates their high achievement, internality and social maturity [4; 8]. During classes, students-creators are actively involved in communicative interaction with a teacher and other students, being aimed at achieving truth and developing their own creative and original position on issues discussed. Their intention is not to overshadow other students with their own erudition, but to achieve an understanding of the problem that will be clear and obvious to all participants in the communication process. And in this sense, they realize the practice of reaching agreement, which, according to J. Habermas, is a sign of communicativeness [14, p. 199]. The cluster of student-creators, according to the results of the aforementioned study of L. Sokuryanskaya, accounts for about 20% of modern students in Ukraine, Russia and Belarus.

Hence, we have considered three educational strategies (the strategy

of “investing in a diploma”, the strategy of “career success” and the strategy of self-realization in the professional sphere), the first two of which are instrumental. Let us try to understand the reasons for this situation; why did instrumental educational practices become dominant in the post-Soviet society (as it was shown above, about 80% of students chose instrumental strategies of “investing in a diploma” and “career success”)? We have established three groups of factors that could contribute to such instrumentalization of the educational sphere.

Firstly, it is necessary to mention “technical” reasons that were the consequence of the higher education reform as a result of joining the Bologna process. In this context, the opinion of L. Sokuryanskaya is interesting. She drew parallels between the introduction of the unified state exam (in Ukraine – external independent testing) and the 100-point system for assessing students’ knowledge, on the one hand, and negative changes in the field of educational motivations of students on the other. “The introduction of external independent testing provoked an irresponsible attitude of students to those disciplines in which they are not tested. This led to a narrowing of the students’ outlook and erudition, a decrease in the intellectual potential of the students as future specialists; we are witnessing an increase in the irresponsibility of students; unfortunately, for most modern students not knowledge is important, but the points they receive for the performance of certain tasks” [11, p.58-59]. Such changes in educational practices form the habitus of minimalism in cognitive demands manifested in the orientation towards attaining the minimum of knowledge necessary for obtaining an optimal assessment and, as a result, generating an instrumental attitude towards education as a mean (and not as self-value).

Secondly, it is necessary to point out the presence of a semantic connection between the instrumental attitude to life and externalism, the essence of which is to impose responsibility for one’s own life, for one’s success/failure on people around or organizations, state or fate. The externalists are not inclined to make efforts to change their lives, to expand their self-consciousness and to deepen their understanding of educational or professional topics; they simply “go with the flow”. Since the externalist is alienated from active life, he/she develops an instrumental attitude to the world and to people, preferring to see in everything and everyone only

means which can be used with a large or less success. And, on the contrary, there is a semantic connection between internalism (characterized by an internal locus of control, a high level of life and social achievement and responsibility) and communicative practices aimed at gaining mutual understanding in different life situations [5; 7].

Students who choose the strategy of self-realization in the professional sphere are internalists with the prevailing communicative life attitudes; students who have chosen the strategy of “investing in a diploma” take external positions preferring instrumental life practices. It is possible to hypothesize that just externalists prevail among modern youth, and this is the reason why the most typical for modern students are the instrumental attitude to education. Indirectly, this hypothesis is confirmed by the results of a sociological all-Ukrainian monitoring conducted by the Institute of Sociology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, according to which a significant percentage of Ukrainians (about 50%) believe that their life largely depends on external circumstances, while only 21.4% state that their life activities are more dependent on themselves” [12, p.491]. It can be assumed that among students one can observe similar proportions in the ratio of externalism-internalism.

Third, to explain the dominance of the “investing in a diploma” strategy, it is worth mentioning the deficit hypothesis proposed by R. Inglehart: for low-income societies, where survival values are on the agenda, material values become dominant. If a young man or woman has socialized in a situation of relative poverty, then they will assimilate (consciously or unconsciously) the material values that are typical for such societies. It can be concluded that in post-Soviet countries where the level of well-being of the population is not high enough, the material life-oriented strategies become quite expected. The fact that students are massively focused on instrumental practices of achieving material well-being (and much less often think about the issues of self-realization in their profession) is reflection (or refraction) of the social situation of “material wealth deficit”.

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